

1 Variations in hazard during earthquake
2 sequences between 1995 and 2018 in western
3 Greece as evaluated by a Bayesian ETAS model

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30 **SUMMARY**

31 Forecasting the spatio-temporal occurrence of events is at the core of Operational Earthquake
32 Forecasting, which is of great interest for risk management, particularly during ongoing seismic
33 sequences. Epidemic type aftershock sequence (ETAS) models are powerful tools to estimate the
34 occurrence of events during earthquake sequences. In this context, a robust seismicity forecasting
35 framework based on Bayesian-inference has been adapted to the Patras and Aegio region in western
36 Greece (one of the most seismically active parts of Mediterranean), and an incremental adaptive
37 algorithm is introduced to train the priors for ETAS model parameters. The seismicity forecasting is
38 capable of accounting for uncertainty in the model parameters as well as variations in the sequence of
39 events that may happen during the forecasting interval. Six seismic sequences between 1995 and 2018
40 were selected with mainshock moment magnitudes $M_w \geq 6.0$. The ETAS model was adapted for each
41 seismic sequence. The number of forecasted events with $M_w \geq 4.5$ and their spatial distribution was
42 retrospectively compared with the as-recorded earthquake catalogue, confirming a good agreement
43 between the forecasts and observations. The results show that the adapted model can be employed
44 immediately after a severe mainshock to statistically predict potentially damaging earthquakes during
45 the ongoing seismic sequence. The seismicity forecasts were translated to short-term daily exceedance
46 rates for different thresholds of peak ground acceleration. The results reveal that the seismic hazard
47 increased by up to 33 times in the case of the damaging 1995 M_w 6.5 earthquake in the city of Aegio.
48 However, the results confirmed that in all six studied sequences, the increased seismic hazard decayed
49 rapidly during the two days after the mainshock, and remained relatively high in the following days
50 (roughly ten times the long-term time-independent hazard).

51 **Keywords**

52 Earthquake interaction; forecasting and prediction; Earthquake hazards; Computational seismology.

53 **1 INTRODUCTION**

54 Estimating time-dependent probabilities of occurrence of potentially damaging earthquakes are at the
55 heart of Operational Earthquake Forecasting (OEF) (Jordan et al. 2014). The output of OEF is often
56 given in terms of probability changes due to time-dependent (over the order of days to months)
57 seismicity. These probabilities can be used by emergency managers to communicate with the public

58 (Jordan and Jones 2010; Goltz 2015; Roeloffs and Goltz 2017; McBride et al. 2020; Field and Minler
59 2018; Douglas and Azarbakht 2021; Azarbakht et al. 2021). Epidemic type aftershock sequence
60 (ETAS) is a family of spatio-temporal point process models providing estimates of the time-
61 dependent seismicity over a predefined aftershock zone (Ogata 1988; Ogata 1998). ETAS models
62 show promising results in forecasting aftershocks and perform quite well in prospectively forecasting
63 the seismicity within various operational frameworks (e.g. Marzocchi and Lombardi 2009; Zhuang
64 2011; Marzocchi and Murru 2012; Marzocchi et al. 2014; Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017; Cattania et
65 al. 2018; Kourouklas et al. 2020). According to the study by Console et al. (2007), the ETAS model is
66 the best model for describing short-term seismicity (see also Zhuang et al. 2011). ETAS is an
67 epidemic stochastic point process that considers every event as a potential trigger for subsequent
68 events, thus, generalising the modified Omori (MO) aftershock decay model (Zhang and Shcherbakov
69 2016, see also Utsu 1961; Utsu and Ogata 1995). In other words, the ETAS model is capable of
70 accounting for the triggering effects of all events in the earthquake catalogue prior to the considered
71 forecasting time interval. It is worth emphasising that an ETAS model's time-dependent seismicity
72 rate can be transformed into a time-dependent hazard model via Probabilistic Seismic Hazard
73 Analysis (PSHA, Cornell 1968; McGuire 1995), as is discussed in the last section of this article.

74 In the present article, a simulation-based framework is employed for both Bayesian updating of
75 spatio-temporal ETAS model parameters as well as to obtain robust estimates of the spatial
76 distribution of events in a prescribed forecasting time interval after a mainshock (see Ebrahimian and
77 Jalayer 2017). The term "robust" here relates to the concept of *robust reliability* (Papadimitriou et al.
78 2001, Beck and Au 2002), which implies both the uncertainties in ETAS model parameters and those
79 related to the occurrence of events in the forecasting interval are considered. The Bayesian inference
80 framework allows the model parameters to be updated with time since the mainshock. In other words,
81 the model adapts itself to the new conditions that the seismicity variations dictate. To clarify, the
82 robust forecasting terminology implies that several sets of model parameters are used through the
83 simulation algorithm instead of using a set of constant model parameters, as is discussed in the
84 methodology section (see also Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017). A Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC)

85 simulation scheme (Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017; Omi et al. 2015; Papadimitriou et al. 2001) is used
86 to sample directly from the conditional posterior probability distributions of the ETAS model
87 parameters. This forecasting framework accounts for two sources of uncertainty: (1) the uncertainty in
88 the ETAS model parameters conditioned on the available catalogue of observed events prior to the
89 forecasting interval's origin time, and (2) the uncertainty in the simulated sequence of events during
90 the forecasting time interval. The outcomes of this framework are in terms of the spatial distribution
91 of the forecasted events and consequently the mean and confidence interval for the estimated number
92 of events, corresponding to a given forecasting interval. The latter results are then converted to
93 seismic hazard estimates, here short-term (hours to weeks) probabilities of exceeding different levels
94 of peak ground acceleration (*PGA*), which is chosen as the ground-motion intensity measure because
95 of its common use in seismic hazard mapping.

96 This article aims to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed Bayesian framework and
97 retrospectively study the aftershock seismicity and hazard forecasts in the Patras and Aegio region in
98 western Greece. This area is chosen for this study since it is in one of Europe's highest seismicity
99 regions with numerous recent earthquake sequences, and it is a testbed of the TURNkey project¹.

100 The seismicity characteristics of the region and the available literature are reviewed in the next
101 section. Following this, the input data and the selected earthquake sequences are discussed. Then,
102 following a brief description of the employed forecasting framework, the retrospective spatio-
103 temporal forecasting of seismicity in the region is studied using this methodology. Subsequently, a
104 daily PSHA is presented by combining the seismicity forecasts with three ground-motion models. The
105 article ends with some brief conclusions.

106 **2 REGION OF STUDY**

107 The geodynamic characteristics of the study region are comprehensively discussed in Karakostas et al.
108 (2020). The study area in western Greece includes the third-largest (in terms of population) city in
109 Greece, Patras, with many essential infrastructures, including a large port. There are also many public

¹ Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions (<https://earthquake-turnkey.eu/>)

110 buildings, schools and heritage monuments. Additionally, the Rio–Antirrio bridge crosses the Gulf of
111 Corinth near Patras. This is one of the world’s longest multi-span cable-stayed bridges and the longest
112 of the fully suspended type. The town of Aegio is also located in the region, which is famous for a
113 topographic plateau across a major fault (the cause of the destructive earthquake on 15 June 1995).
114 There are also two smaller towns, Kalavryta and Lidorikion, in the region. In this section, we briefly
115 summarise the recent literature on seismic hazard and previous earthquake forecasts for this region.

116 Both time-independent and time-dependent seismic hazards in Greece were investigated in terms of
117 macroseismic intensity by Papaioannou and Papazachos (2000) for 144 cities, towns, and villages.
118 They concluded that the time-dependent seismic hazard results are in good agreement with the
119 observed seismicity during the period 150 to 1995. A detailed areal-source seismic zonation model for
120 shallow earthquakes in the broader Aegean area, containing 113 zones, was proposed by Vamvakaris
121 et al. (2016). This model was based on seismicity and the available seismotectonic and neotectonic
122 information to represent active faulting characteristics. A detailed investigation of catalogue
123 completeness for the recent instrumental period was also conducted. The seismicity parameters, such
124 as Gutenberg-Richter values for the 113 proposed zones, were calculated, and their spatial distribution
125 was also considered. A review of the official seismic hazard maps in Greece was given by Tsapanos
126 (2008).

127 Spatio-temporal earthquake clustering in the western Corinth gulf was investigated by Karagianni et
128 al. (2013) by considering geological, seismological, and geodetic aspects. The results reveal
129 complicated tectonic behaviour and strong indications that seismicity in the area is not random and
130 forms distinctive clusters. Console et al. (2006) applied various forecasting algorithms to the Greek
131 catalogue for two periods: 1966-1980 and 1981-2002. The forecasting capability was statistically
132 assessed by using the log-likelihood method. Their results revealed that short-term and long-term
133 methods performed much better than time-invariant models. Gospodinov and Rotondi (2006) and
134 Gospodinov et al. (2007) studied the temporal decay in eight Greek aftershock sequences since 1975
135 using a Restricted ETAS model (RETAS). The RETAS model assumes that only aftershocks of
136 magnitudes bigger than or equal to a given threshold can trigger secondary events. Karakostas et al.

137 (2014) focused on forecasting, temporally and spatially, the 2013 Mw 5.8 north Aegean seismic
138 sequence. They employed different statistical methods to simulate the aftershock sequence, including
139 an ETAS model with pre-calibrated parameters. Their results indicate a significant Probability Gain
140 (PG) of more than 20 times the background probability during the first days of the considered
141 aftershock sequence. Latoussakis et al. (1991), Latoussakis and Drakatos (1994), and Drakatos and
142 Latoussakis (1996) studied the possibility of forecasting large earthquakes in Greece during different
143 sequences. They used the MO formula and noted its acceptable accuracy. Telesca et al. (2001)
144 analysed the temporal properties of Greek aftershock sequences using the MO model. A physics-
145 based and statistical earthquake forecasting approach was applied by Segou (2016) to the continental
146 rift zone of the Corinth Gulf, by implementing a retrospective forecast of events with magnitudes
147 greater than or equal to 3 for the time period 1995-2013. This study revealed that the joint
148 implementation of physics-based approaches and the statistical ETAS model is beneficial for future
149 OEF systems. Kourouklas et al. (2020) investigated short-term spatio-temporal clustering of Greek
150 seismicity from 2008 to 2018. The employed ETAS model used maximum-likelihood estimation
151 through a simulated annealing approach. The discrepancies between the ETAS model forecasts and
152 the observations were assessed by residual analysis. The model performed well except for the 2008
153 sequence when five $M_w > 6$ earthquakes occurred. Finally, the short-term seismicity of the central
154 Ionian Islands was studied by Mangira et al. (2020), revealing that the employed ETAS clustering
155 model provides reliable forecasts of the aftershock activity for this region.

156 To be complementary to the available literature, the current study uses the most recent seismic data
157 for the region from 1995 to 2018, which contains six earthquakes with $M_w \geq 6$, as explained in detail
158 in the next section.

159 **3 INPUT DATA AND SELECTED SEQUENCES**

160 The International Seismological Centre (ISC, last access 2020) earthquake catalogue (Bondár and
161 Storchak 2011; ISC 2020) was used to collect data from the previous three decades in the study
162 region. It was concluded that six severe mainshocks with their triggered aftershock sequences are

163 distinguishable since the catastrophic 1995 Aegio event. It is assumed that these six sequences are
164 sufficient samples to have both a set of consistent and modern instrumental data, and sufficient
165 sequences to study the potential variation in model parameters. The spatial and temporal
166 characteristics of the ISC catalogue for the study area between 1995 and 2018 (including the six
167 seismic sequences A to F) are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively. The cumulative number
168 of earthquakes with $M_w \geq 3$ is also shown in Figure 2, indicating heightened seismicity around the
169 selected sequences. Greek national catalogues were not used here; however, they are identical with
170 the ISC catalogue beyond the magnitude of completeness. In Greece, there are two institutions
171 reporting phases (bulletin data) to ISC: NOA and Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH). In
172 other words, there is no common national bulletin in Greece, although, since 2007, there is a unified
173 network sharing waveform data with the public. NOA is the official seismic monitoring agency in
174 Greece, which provides the majority of Greek data to ISC. Nevertheless, the ISC reports some small
175 earthquakes (particularly in northern Greece) using AUTH data. Therefore, the ISC catalogue is the
176 most rational choice for the current study.

177 The selected earthquake sequences are listed in Table 1, covering mainshocks with moment
178 magnitude $M_w \geq 6$ between 1995 and 2018. The distances between each mainshock's epicentre and
179 the two studied cities (Patras and Aegio) are also provided in Table 1 (sequences A and C are the
180 closest to Patras and Aegio, including sequence A, which was only 23 km from Aegio). These
181 differences in distance will influence the seismic hazard assessed at the considered locations, as
182 discussed below.

183
184 Figure 1. The spatial distribution of the earthquakes between 1995 and 2018 in the study area. The selected
185 seismic sequences are indicated by the capital letters next to the mainshock epicentre (see Table 1).
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189 Figure 2. (top): The events with $M_w \geq 3$ versus time in the ISC earthquake catalogue between 1995 and 2018 in
 190 the study area, including the labelled sequences in Table 1, (bottom): The cumulative number of events with
 191 $M_w \geq 3$ between 1995 and 2018.

192

193 Table 1. The selected sequences between 1995 and 2018 with mainshock magnitude $M_w \geq 6$, mainshock
 194 occurrence time, and the distances to the cities of Patras and Aegio.

Sequence Label	Lat. (N)	Lon. (E)	Mainshock Magnitude (Mw)	Mainshock Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	Hour:Minute	Distance to Patras (km)	Distance to Aegio (km)
A	38.39	22.28	6.5	15/06/1995	00:15	50	23
B	37.50	20.80	6.6	18/11/1997	13:07	116	140
C	37.96	21.45	6.1	08/06/2008	12:25	40	64
D	38.19	20.51	6.1	26/01/2014	13:55	107	137
E	38.68	20.53	6.5	17/11/2015	07:10	115	143

F	37.53	20.62	6.8	25/10/2018	22:54	126	151
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196 4 METHODOLOGY

197 Seismicity forecasts over periods of hours/days/weeks are crucial for emergency responders and
 198 decision-makers seeking to mitigate risk since there is a high chance of aftershocks during this period.

199 It is clear that forecasting damaging earthquakes have a higher priority than forecasting small events,
 200 which is practically impossible. Therefore, this study's focus is to forecast events with magnitudes \geq
 201 4.5, which is the cut-off magnitude often considered in European seismic hazard studies (Woessner et
 202 al., 2015). A robust seismicity forecasting framework (Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017) has been
 203 implemented for this study. By pairing the Bayesian inference with an advanced simulation technique
 204 (namely, MCMC) to update the ETAS model parameters, this framework has the unique feature of
 205 considering different sources of uncertainty, i.e. the uncertainties in the ETAS model parameters and
 206 the generated sequence of events within the forecasting interval (sequences are generated based on
 207 samples of the ETAS model parameters).

208 4.1 The epidemic-type aftershock sequence (ETAS) model

209 The ETAS model is a marked spatio-temporal point process (Daley and Vere-Jones 2003), where a
 210 seismic sequence is treated as a point process of inter-event time and epicentres. The magnitude of
 211 each event is an additional observed variable characterizing the point process to become marked. Let
 212 the aftershock zone be defined as set \mathbf{A} in the Cartesian space. The conditional rate of occurrence of
 213 earthquakes at time t with magnitude $\geq m$ in the cell unit centred at the Cartesian coordinate $(x, y) \in$
 214 \mathbf{A} based on the ETAS model is denoted as $\lambda_{\text{ETAS}}(t, x, y, m | \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{seq}_t, M_l)$. The rate λ_{ETAS} is conditioned
 215 on: (1) the vector of ETAS model parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ (defined subsequently); (2) the observation history up
 216 to time t , which expresses the influence of past events $\mathbf{seq}_t = \{(t_j, x_j, y_j, m_j), t_j < t, M_j \geq M_l\}$ where
 217 t_j is the arrival time for the j^{th} event (with $t_j < t$) with magnitude m_j and location $(x_j, y_j) \in \mathbf{A}$; and
 218 (3) the lower cut-off magnitude M_l . The conditional rate λ_{ETAS} can be computed as follows:

$$219 \lambda_{\text{ETAS}}(t, x, y, m | \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{seq}_t, M_l) = e^{-\beta(m-M_l)} \sum_{t_j < t} [K e^{\beta(m_j-M_l)} \frac{K_t}{(t-t_j+c)^p} \frac{K_R}{(r_j^2+d^2)^q}] \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

220 In Equation (1), the background seismicity rate is not considered; this issue will be discussed in the
 221 subsequent section. The vector of ETAS model parameters is defined as $\theta = [K, K_t, K_R, \beta, c, p, d, q]$.
 222 Parameter β is related to the Gutenberg-Richter relation; parameters c and p are similar to those of the
 223 MO's Law defining the decay in time; d and q characterise the spatial distribution of the triggered
 224 events; r_j is the distance between the location (x, y) and the epicentre of the j^{th} event (x_j, y_j) . The
 225 parameter K requires calibration for each forecasting interval and is discussed in the subsequent
 226 section. The parameter K_t is computed so that the time-dependent term $K_t / (t - t_j + c)^p$ over infinite
 227 time will, in the limit, be equal to unity (see Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017 and Lippiello et al. 2012
 228 and 2014), which results in $K_t = (P - 1) \cdot c^{(p-1)}$. Finally, the parameter K_R is normalised such that
 229 integrating the spatial term over infinite space will also, in the limit, be equal to unity (see Ebrahimian
 230 and Jalayer 2017 and Lippiello et al. 2012 and 2014) resulting in $K_r = \frac{(q-1)}{\pi} \cdot d^{2(q-1)}$. In the ETAS
 231 model (Equation 1), the term $K e^{\alpha(M_j - M_t)}$ is called the productivity function and the coefficient α
 232 shows the efficiency of an event in generating aftershock activity (dimension of magnitude⁻¹). It is
 233 assumed herein that $\alpha = \beta$ (for more details, see the parameter α in Ogata and Zhuang 2006). Hence,
 234 in summary, only five model parameters (i.e., $[\beta, c, p, d, q]$) are used in the MCMC updating
 235 framework. The other three parameters ($[K, K_t, K_R]$) are calculated as described above (for more
 236 details, see Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017). It is noted that the generated sample through the MCMC
 237 algorithm is rejected if any of the following conditions hold: (1) any value of the vector $[\beta, c, p, d, q]$
 238 is negative, (2) $p \leq 1$, or (3) $q \leq 1$ (the latter two conditions are described in Ebrahimian and Jalayer
 239 2017). It is also worth mentioning that the focus of the current study is forecasting over a short time
 240 interval (e.g. one day), otherwise, the β coefficient in the productivity function may cause the
 241 population to explode when simulating for a relatively long time period.

242 To clarify, the assumption of equality between the two parameters α and β is a commonly adopted
 243 constraint (see e.g. Seif et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2018; Papadopoulos et al. 2021). When α is
 244 considered to be a free parameter in the ETAS model (i.e. the model parameters become
 245 $[\alpha, \beta, c, p, d, q]$), past studies based on maximum-likelihood estimation (e.g. Marzocchi and Lombardi

2009) or Bayesian parameter estimation (Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2021) showed that $\alpha < \beta$. In particular, the parameter α determines the magnitude dependence of the trigger potential, which is crucial in identifying the underlying triggering mechanism and for forecasting ongoing earthquake sequences (Hainzl et al. 2013). The constraint $\alpha = \beta$ implies self-similarity of the triggering events (i.e. the number of triggered events is proportional to the rupture area of the triggering earthquake, see Papadopoulos et al. 2021). Moreover, it is shown that α might be significantly underestimated (low value of α) due to the incompleteness of the aftershock catalogue and missing data at the early stages of an ongoing seismic sequence (Seif et al. 2017). This issue may be critical in terms of providing operational forecasts in the immediate aftermath of a large earthquake. Moreover, in the study region (Greece), where the recorded catalogue is not rich in low-magnitude events (see Section 4.3), this consideration might underestimate the parameter α . There are also other issues that have a significant influence on the estimation of the parameter α including anisotropic aftershock distribution (Hainzl et al. 2008), potential time-dependent (nonstationary) background rate and transient aseismic forcing (Hainzl et al. 2013, who show that the majority of earthquake clusters in California are compatible with $\alpha = \beta$). Therefore, to avoid these potential biases, we have assumed $\alpha = \beta$ in the current study.

261 4.2 Estimation for the number of aftershocks

262 With reference to Equation (1), let $\lambda_{\text{ETAS}}(t, x, y, m | \boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ be the conditional intensity representing the ETAS rate of occurrence of events in the forecasting interval $[T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}]$ at time t (elapsed after the main event, or even any arbitrary time reference) with the time of origin at T_o . The observation history \mathbf{seq} is the sequence of N_o events (including the mainshock and the sequence of aftershocks) that took place before the forecasting interval, i.e., in the interval $[T_o, T_{\text{start}})$. This can be expressed as $\mathbf{seq} = \{(t_i, x_i, y_i, m_i), T_o \leq t_i < T_{\text{start}}, m_i \geq M_l, i = 1:N_o\}$. The number of events at the centre point of a given cell centred at (x, y) with magnitude $\geq m$ in the forecasting interval $[T_{\text{start}}, T_{\text{end}}]$, denoted as $N(x, y, m | \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$, can be estimated by:

$$270 \quad N(x, y, m | \mathbf{seq}, M_l) = N_b(x, y, m | M_l) + \int_{T_{\text{start}}}^{T_{\text{end}}} \lambda_{\text{ETAS}}(t, x, y, m | \mathbf{seq}, M_l) dt \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

271 where $N_b(x, y, m|M_l)$ is a constant representing the area's background seismicity. It is equal to the
 272 time-invariant background spatial seismicity rate for magnitudes $> m$ multiplied by the time interval
 273 $(T_{end} - T_{start})$. To clarify, the number of events in the whole cell can be calculated by multiplying N
 274 by the area of the cell. Given a realisation of θ as the vector of ETAS model parameters, parameter K
 275 (of the vector θ) is calibrated such that the number of events with magnitude $\geq M_l$ taking place in the
 276 time interval $[T_o, T_{start})$, over the whole aftershock zone is equal to N_o (see Ebrahimian and Jalayer
 277 2017 for more details). Moreover, one can calculate a plausible value for the rate of occurrence
 278 denoted as $\lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m|\theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$, as shown in Equation (1). A robust estimate (Ebrahimian and
 279 Jalayer 2017) of the average number of events in the cell centred at (x, y) with a magnitude $\geq m$ in the
 280 forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$, denoted as $\mathbb{E}[N(x, y, m|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)]$, can be calculated over the domain
 281 of the model parameters Ω_θ :

$$282 \quad \mathbb{E}[N(x, y, m|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)] = N_b(x, y, m|M_l) + \int_{\Omega_\theta} \left(\int_{T_{start}}^{T_{end}} \lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m|\mathbf{seq}, M_l) dt \right) p(\theta|\mathbf{seq}, M_l) d\theta \text{ (Eq. 3)}$$

283 where $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ denotes the expectation, and $p(\theta|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ is the conditional posterior probability density
 284 function (PDF) for θ given the \mathbf{seq} and the lower cut-off magnitude M_l . The PDF $p(\theta|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ can
 285 be estimated using Bayesian parameter estimation, which is discussed in Appendix 1. Equation (3)
 286 accounts for the events that took place before the forecasting interval $[T_o, T_{start})$; however, the
 287 triggering effect of the events taking place during the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$ is expected to
 288 play a major role. The robust estimate for the average number of aftershocks (as noted previously)
 289 also considers all the plausible sequences of events that can happen during the forecasting time
 290 interval (see Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017 for a comprehensive discussion). To this end, the sequence
 291 of events taking place during the forecasting interval (denoted herein as \mathbf{seqg}), which is unknown at
 292 the time of forecasts, is simulated. Let us assume that a plausible \mathbf{seqg} is defined as the events within
 293 the forecasting interval defined as $\mathbf{seqg} = \{(IAT_i, x_i, y_i, m_i), T_{start} \leq t_i \leq T_{end}, m_i \geq M_l\}$, where
 294 $IAT_i = t_i - t_{i-1}$ stands for the inter-arrival time. The robust estimate for the number of aftershocks in
 295 Equation (3) should also consider all the plausible sequences of events \mathbf{seqg} (i.e., the domain $\Omega_{\mathbf{seqg}}$)
 296 that can happen during the forecasting time interval, as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}[N(x, y, m|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)] = N_b(x, y, m|M_l) + \int_{\Omega_{\theta}} \left[\int_{\Omega_{\mathbf{seq}}} \left(\int_{T_{start}}^{T_{end}} \lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m|\mathbf{seqg}, \theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l) dt \right) p(\mathbf{seqg}|\theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l) d\mathbf{seqg} \right] p(\theta|\mathbf{seq}, M_l) d\theta$$

(Eq. 4)

where $p(\mathbf{seqg}|\theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ is the PDF for the generated sequence \mathbf{seqg} given that θ and \mathbf{seq} are known and $\lambda_{ETAS}(t, x, y, m|\mathbf{seqg}, \theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ is the space-time clustering ETAS model considering also the sequence of events taking place within the forecasting interval. The robust estimation in Equation (4) implies that a set of possible model parameters is used to estimate the conditional number of events $N(x, y, m|\mathbf{seq}, M_l)$ rather than a single set of model parameters.

The proposed algorithm is demonstrated for six independent seismic sequences in the region (see Section 5). The employed algorithm is shown to successfully forecast aftershocks in all the six considered sequences. The conditional estimation of N (see Equation 4) can be used further for short-term time-dependent PSHA. The 2013 European Seismic Hazard Model (ESHM13) (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015) has been used in the current study to define the background seismicity in Equation (2) to Equation (4). The Kernel-smoothed stochastic rate model considering seismicity and fault moment release (SEIFA-model) has been employed to define each cell's background seismicity rate in the aftershock zone (Woessner et al. 2015).

4.3 The incremental adaptive training algorithm to obtain priors for the ETAS model parameters

Defining prior values for the model parameters θ is a challenging task. In Greece the aftershock sequences are not particularly productive and/or well-reported, i.e., the magnitude of completeness (M_c) varies between 2.7 to 4.5 for different locations and catalogue lengths (see Vamvakaris et al. 2016). This relatively high magnitude of completeness makes defining the prior values even more challenging. It is not reasonable to wait for a long time after a mainshock to obtain a satisfactory catalogue (for the period after the mainshock only) to initiate the forecasting procedure (especially in the context of operational earthquake forecasting). In other words, we would need to wait a long time after a mainshock (in aftershock sequences of low productivity or high magnitude of completeness) so that sufficient events occur to obtain a complete catalogue if we insist on using only the events

324 following a mainshock (sequence-specific). To clarify, as a solution, it is convenient to “borrow”
325 events from a time window before the mainshock to calibrate the model parameters and consequently
326 update it during the aftershock sequence. Therefore, an *incremental adaptive training algorithm* has
327 been developed and proposed in this study to estimate a set of reasonable priors for the ETAS model
328 parameters θ to start the forecast algorithm almost immediately after a mainshock (see Figure 3). It is
329 worth emphasising that the proposed adaptive approach is only used for the first round of the
330 forecasting algorithm. The sequence-specific catalogue (from the mainshock’s origin time) is then
331 used for the second round (i.e., the second day in this study) of the forecasting trials and so forth. As
332 shown in Figure 3, the proposed algorithm starts its computations from ‘M’ months before the
333 forecast interval and chooses several arbitrary subsets of ‘E’ events with magnitude $\geq M_c$. It is worth
334 mentioning that M_c is sequence-specific and is calculated for each sequence separately. In the case of
335 the first round, where the adaptive algorithm in Figure 3 is employed, if we face a quiescent period
336 before the mainshock, we lengthen the catalogue prior to the mainshock to obtain sufficient data to
337 calibrate the prior parameters of the ETAS model. Additionally, in the case of the second round and
338 so forth, we may face a lack of data in the catalogue after the mainshock for calculation of the
339 magnitude of completeness. This lack of data may be due to low productivity in a specific sequence or
340 the aftershock waves being hidden in the seismic waves of the larger events (Lippiello et al. 2016 and
341 2019). In this case, we move the catalogue origin time T_0 back a couple of days before the mainshock,
342 with the aim of having a catalogue that is sufficient to calculate M_c .

343 Normally-distributed prior model parameters (mean values of $b=1$, $c=0.03$, $p=1$, $d=1$, $q=1.5$, all with
344 standard deviation (σ) equal to 0.3, and $\beta = b \cdot \ln 10$) are used for the first subset of the adaptive
345 incremental algorithm, and the MCMC algorithm is used to update these model parameters based on
346 the first subset catalogue. As an example, the prior and posterior distributions of the ‘c’ model
347 parameter are shown in Figure 4. As seen in Figure 4, sample posterior intervals are simulated by the
348 MCMC algorithm, and consequently, a normal distribution is fitted to the posterior numerical
349 histograms. In other words, an advantage of the currently employed model is that the model

350 parameters are not constant during a seismic sequence, which is in contrast with ETAS models based
351 on the maximum-likelihood approach.

352 Subsequently, the previous subset's posterior distributions are used as the prior distributions for the
353 next subset. This procedure repeats until we reach the last subset, which ends before the starting time
354 of the forecast (T_{start}). Each subset is also checked so that it covers at least 'D' days of the catalogue,
355 i.e. if 'E' events happen in less than 'D' days, we increase the subset's time window to cover at least
356 'D' days.

357 This proposed algorithm ensures that the final prior distributions for the ETAS model parameters have
358 been trained based on the previous 'M' months catalogue. For example, for Sequence F (see Table 1),
359 the employed catalogue goes back a year before the mainshock (27-1-2018 to 25-10-2018). Hence, as
360 seen in Table 2, we start from 27 January 2018 until the date which provides subsets of at least 50
361 events with magnitude $\geq M_c$ (equal to 4.1 in this case based on the approach of Wiemer 2001) and
362 covers at least a minimum duration of 30 days. The minimum of 50 events guarantees the proper
363 numerical MCMC updating of the ETAS model parameters (this was empirically verified by the
364 authors); nevertheless, considering a minimum value for D (equal to 30 days herein) will also provide
365 a trade-off between the number of events and the time span in which they took place. The first row in
366 Table 2 indicates that the first subset begins on 27 January 2018 and ends on 14 March 2018, which
367 contains 71 events with $M \geq 4.1$. These events were primarily used in the MCMC Bayesian updating
368 algorithm to update the prior model parameters. The updated five (mean) model parameters are also
369 provided in the first row of Table 2. The first row of Table 2 is used as prior information (the mean
370 value, the corresponding σ and the normal distribution assumption) for the second row. This
371 procedure was repeated until the last row in Table 2, which is before the forecasting date, i.e. at 00:00
372 UTC on 26 October 2018 (almost one hour after the mainshock of Sequence F). The proposed
373 incremental adaptive training of the ETAS model parameters needs only the MCMC algorithm to
374 update the ETAS model parameters (subsets 1 to 6 in Table 2). The seismicity forecasting is only
375 performed for the last row in Table 2 (subset 6 in Table 2) in order to provide the spatio-temporal
376 distribution of earthquakes in the forecasting interval of interest, as discussed in the next section.

377 The adaptive training of the ETAS model parameters provides the opportunity to initiate earthquake
 378 forecasting almost immediately after the occurrence of a mainshock, especially in regions with
 379 aftershock sequences of low productivity. This is a key forecasting constraint in many high seismicity
 380 regions such as Greece in the first (golden) hours after a severe mainshock, during which the
 381 forecasting results are of utmost importance for first responders. The possibility of earthquake
 382 forecasting immediately after a severe mainshock is of great interest to researchers (e.g. Lippiello et
 383 al. 2016 and 2019). The proposed incremental adaptive training algorithm also provides a rational
 384 framework to continuously update the prior ETAS model parameters used in an OEF engine on a
 385 regular basis. A potential OEF framework may use the last set of updated parameters, when a
 386 magnitude greater than a pre-defined threshold occurs, which can potentially define the mainshock of
 387 interest. In this context, there is no need to consider a very long sequence (e.g., the whole 419 events
 388 in Table 2), which thus overcomes the burden of summing up the triggering properties of all the
 389 events when providing early forecasts. Moreover, there is no need to consider the origin time of the
 390 sequence if the mainshock is not preceded by foreshocks.

391 Table 2. The incremental adaptive training of the ETAS model parameters for sequence F (see Table 1).

Number of subsets	Start date (dd-mm-yyyy)	End date (dd-mm-yyyy)	No. of events with $M \geq M_c$	β	c	d	p	q
1	27-01-2018	14-03-2018	71	1.681	0.044	1.014	1.803	1.207
2	17-03-2018	23-04-2018	70	1.679	0.048	1.014	2.050	1.224
3	24-04-2018	17-06-2018	70	1.681	0.054	1.012	2.172	1.230
4	17-06-2018	06-08-2018	70	1.682	0.058	1.010	2.443	1.225
5	06-08-2018	01-10-2018	70	1.682	0.064	1.009	2.535	1.226
6	01-10-2018	25-10-2018	68	1.682	0.065	1.010	2.556	1.227

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393
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Figure 3. The flowchart of the incremental adaptive training algorithm to obtain the ETAS prior model parameters.

395

396 Figure 4. The MCMC updating for the example of the ‘c’ model parameter, showing the prior and posterior
 397 distributions.

398 We summarize the proposed methodology’s steps as follows:

- 399 1- Use the incremental adaptive training methodology to obtain prior ETAS model parameters
 400 before a mainshock. This set of model parameters is used for the first forecasting attempt after a
 401 mainshock.
- 402 2- Use the sequence-specific catalogue (between the mainshock’s origin time and the start of the
 403 forecasting interval) to obtain the ETAS model parameters for the second forecasting trial and so
 404 forth. If the catalogue is not sufficient to estimate the magnitude of completeness, then the
 405 catalogue is extended by days/months before the mainshock to obtain sufficient data.
- 406 3- To estimate the ETAS model parameters conditioned on the events that have already taken place
 407 in the ongoing seismic sequence and before the beginning of the forecasting interval, an MCMC
 408 simulation scheme is used to sample directly from the conditional posterior probability
 409 distribution for ETAS model parameters. This ETAS model parameter updating is applied to the
 410 selected catalogue (from either Step 1 or Step 2 above).

- 411 4- Perform many (200 in our study) sequence simulations based on the generated plausible
 412 sequences of events that may occur during the forecasting interval (the real sequence is unknown
 413 at the time of forecasting).
- 414 5- Use Equation (4) to estimate the spatial distribution of the forecasted events and consequently the
 415 estimated number of events corresponding to a given forecasting interval with their confidence
 416 intervals. The background seismicity can also be included.
- 417 6- Employ Equation (6) (see Section 6) to convert forecasted seismicity results into time-dependent
 418 seismic hazard estimates.

419 **5 SEISMICITY FORECASTING RESULTS**

420 The study area in Figure 2 is defined between 20-23E and 37-39N and is meshed with a grid size of
 421 0.05×0.05 degrees, which is the same grid size as ESHM13 (Woessner et al. 2015). This choice
 422 facilitates the implementation of the seismicity results in the PSHA. This area is the same as in
 423 previous studies on these earthquake sequences (e.g. Karakostas et al., 2020). The forecast interval is
 424 defined as one day (24 hours), and T_{start} is set at 00:00 UTC. Starting with the most recent mainshock
 425 (i.e., sequence F), T_{start} is almost one hour after the mainshock. Sequence F's mainshock had a
 426 magnitude M_w of 6.8 and occurred at 37.53N and 20.62E, which is near the southwest corner of the
 427 considered aftershock zone (Figure 5, see also Figure 2 and Table 1). It is worth mentioning that
 428 ESHM13 (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015) has been used throughout this paper to define
 429 the background seismicity as an input to the ETAS model.

430 The forecasted short-term spatial distribution of seismicity in terms of the mean plus 2σ (98%
 431 confidence interval) in the study area is shown in Figure 5, for a forecast interval of one day (24
 432 hours) following T_{start} of 00:00 UTC on 26 October 2018. The observed earthquakes of interest that
 433 occurred within the corresponding forecasting interval are also illustrated as coloured dots
 434 (distinguished by magnitude). The colour bar in Figure 5 indicates the forecasted number of
 435 occurrences (per forecast time interval and per km^2) of events with a magnitude $\geq M_l$ (we set
 436 $M_l = M_c = 4.1$ in this case). M_c is calculated (Wiemer 2001) based on the sequence of events (see **seq** in

437 Equation 2), which contains 68 observed data from 1-10-2018 to 25-10-2018 (see the last row in
438 Table 2), and eight aftershocks occurred during the 66 minutes between the mainshock time (22:54
439 UTC) and T_{start} (00:00 UTC). Only eight aftershocks with $M \geq M_c$ took place after the mainshock up to
440 T_{start} ; hence, as explained in the previous section, we used the catalogue before the mainshock origin
441 time (see the last row in Table 2) to overcome this shortcoming and to incrementally obtain the model
442 parameters' prior values.

443 As shown in Figure 5, higher seismicity is forecasted at the closest distances to the mainshock's
444 epicentre. The probabilities of exceeding different magnitude thresholds (from 4.5 to 7.5) are shown
445 in Table 3 for all sequences (A to F in Table 1) and the first forecasting day following the given
446 mainshocks. The upper limit for the magnitude is assumed to be 7.5 since the maximum magnitude in
447 ESHM13 (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015) for all the 14 SEIFA area sources in the study
448 area are between 7.2 and 8.1. It is worth noting that the probabilities shown in Table 3 refer to an
449 event occurring anywhere inside the study area and cannot be interpreted as a forecast of a specific
450 event at a particular location. These probabilities are the integration of forecasted numbers over all
451 cells (covering the whole study region). For example, the probability of having $M_w \geq 4.5$ during the
452 first day following a mainshock anywhere in the whole study area is equal to $0.999\bar{9}$ (=1.00) in the
453 case of sequence F. This forecast is reasonable since there are 32 observed events with $M_w \geq 4.5$ in
454 this forecasting time interval (Figure 5 and Table 3).

455 The forecasted number of events, within the aftershock zone, with $M_w \geq 4.5$ (which is the minimum
456 magnitude assumed in ESHM13 for seismic hazard calculation) is also shown in Table 3, indicate the
457 forecasted 50th percentile (the median value, equivalent to the logarithmic mean in an arithmetic
458 scale), the 84th percentile (logarithmic mean plus one logarithmic σ in an arithmetic scale), and the
459 98th percentile (logarithmic mean plus two logarithmic σ in an arithmetic scale), respectively. The
460 observed number of events with a magnitude greater than 4.5 is also shown in Table 3 for the purpose
461 of comparison. As seen in Table 3, the forecasted numbers of events are in good agreement with the
462 observed data. This is an inherent criterion to intuitively assess the quality of the forecasting

463 algorithm. To study this agreement more, we estimated the seismicity for different forecasting time
 464 intervals. Besides, as seen in Table 4, the results (including statistical percentiles) are provided by
 465 repeating the current forecasting algorithm for nine different forecasting time intervals, all with the
 466 same T_{start} (i.e., 00:00 UTC on 26 October 2018). The distribution of the forecasted number of events
 467 shows good agreement with the observed catalogue, as reported in Table 4. Therefore, the 24-hour
 468 forecasting time interval is chosen for further investigations; this is also a reasonable time interval for
 469 risk management purposes (see also Ebrahimian et al. 2013 and 2014). It is worth mentioning that the
 470 forecasted number of events is calculated as a real number, but is shown in Table 4 after rounding to
 471 the closest integer value. Therefore, some percentiles for a given time interval become identical in
 472 Table 4.

473 In addition, the N-test (Zechar et al. 2010) was employed to assess the quality of the forecasts. The N-
 474 test is intended to measure (in a probabilistic manner) how well the forecasted number of earthquakes
 475 matches the observed number of events. According to this test, we fit a Poisson distribution to the
 476 forecasted number of events (N_{fore}) with a magnitude greater than a threshold, which is actually the
 477 expected number of events in the forecasting interval that we have estimated. Then, we measure if the
 478 observed number of events (N_{obs}) with a magnitude greater than a threshold is not located in the tails
 479 of the Poisson distribution. To this end, we estimate two probability terms that should be greater than
 480 a pre-defined value P_{eff} : as written in Equation (5).

$$\begin{aligned}
 481 \quad P(n \leq N_{obs} | N_{fore}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{N_{obs}} \frac{(N_{fore})^n e^{-N_{fore}}}{n!} > P_{eff} \\
 482 \quad P(n \geq N_{obs} | N_{fore}) &= 1 - P(n \leq N_{obs} - 1 | N_{fore}) = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{(N_{obs}-1)} \frac{(N_{fore})^n e^{-N_{fore}}}{n!} > P_{eff} \\
 483 & \hspace{20em} (Eq. 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

484 The above expression guaranties that the real case of N_{obs} will not be within the tails of our forecast. It
 485 is worth mentioning that the value for P_{eff} is set to 0.025 to reflect the 95% confidence interval. As
 486 seen in Table 4, the N-test column has two numbers in each cell, representing the first and second
 487 integrals in Equation (5), respectively. The employed N-test confirms that, in all forecast cases, the
 488 N_{obs} is not located within the tails of our forecast. However, providing the statistical distribution of

489 N_{fore} (see Table 4) is more feasible in the sense that instead of assigning a Poisson distribution to the
 490 forecasted number of events, it estimates directly the distribution of the forecast and computes its
 491 percentiles (i.e., 50th, 16th, 84th, 2nd and 98th). In this way, one can judge how well the forecasted
 492 number of earthquakes matches N_{obs} . Besides, as seen in Figures 5 and 6, the spatial distribution of
 493 forecasted events are in very good agreement with the observed events, which again demonstrates the
 494 accuracy of the employed algorithm.

495

496 Figure 5. The spatial distribution of the seismicity (the map reports the mean+2σ confidence interval, i.e. 98th
 497 percentile, for the number of events per km²) in the aftershock zone for 26 October 2018 (sequence F in
 498 Table1). The forecast interval is 24 hours, starting from 00:00 UTC. The probability of having a magnitude
 499 greater than or equal to a given magnitude is shown in the figure’s bottom-left corner. The forecasted numbers
 500 of events with $M \geq 4.5$ are shown in the bottom-right corner. The first, second, and third numbers indicate the
 501 50th, 84th and 98th percentiles. The fourth number (in the parenthesis) indicates the observed number of events.

502

503 Table 3. Comparison between the forecasted number of events (and the corresponding statistical distribution)
 504 with $M \geq 4.5$ and the observed data in the case of all sequences for the first day after the mainshock. The
 505 probabilities of exceeding different magnitude thresholds (from 4.5 to 7.5) over the whole aftershock zone are
 506 also shown.

Sequence Label	Number of forecasted events with $M \geq 4.5$			Observed	P($M \geq m$) over the aftershock zone			
	50 th percentile	84 th percentile	98 th percentile		m=4.5	m=5.5	m=6.5	m=7.5
A	2	2	2	2	.9	.2	.03	.003
B	3	4	4	4	1	.3	.04	.005
C	3	3	4	0	.9	.2	.03	.003
D	1	1	1	4	.6	.1	.01	.001
E	4	5	7	3	1	.5	.1	.02
F	20	24	35	32	1	1	.5	.1

507
508

509 Table 4. Comparison between the forecasted number of events (and the corresponding statistical distribution)
510 with $M \geq 4.5$ and the observed data in the case of sequence F for different forecasting intervals. The forecasting
511 start time, T_{start} , is 00:00 UTC on 26 October 2018.

Forecasting interval	Number of forecasted events with $M \geq 4.5$					Observed	N-test
	2 nd percentile	16 th percentile	50 th percentile	84 th percentile	98 th percentile		
6 hours	6	7	7	9	12	11	.946, .098
12 hours	9	10	12	15	20	19	.978, .037
1 day	13	16	20	24	35	32	.983, .026
2 days	19	23	30	42	83	39	.953, .064
3 days	23	30	39	57	92	45	.850, .187
4 days	28	36	48	68	109	50	.648, .405
5 days	35	43	61	82	149	61	.483, .567
6 days	39	49	66	93	181	63	.386, .660
7 days	44	54	76	111	189	67	.227, .807

512

513 Another advantage of the seismicity forecasting model is its ability to forecast repeatedly during the
514 short duration of most aftershock sequences within an operational framework. Hence, the forecasting
515 model has been run repeatedly every day until seven days following the mainshock (see Table 5). To
516 clarify, we only used the incremental adaptive training of the parameters in the case of forecasting for
517 26 October (the first row in Table 5), for which **seq** contained 68 events and was defined previously
518 in this section (see the last row of Table 2). However, for the second-day forecast (second row in
519 Table 5) and for subsequent forecasts, we only used the previous day's posterior distribution (the
520 mean value, the corresponding σ and the normal distribution) as prior values for the next day.

521 Additionally, we only used the catalogue starting from the mainshock up to the T_{start} , in the case of
522 forecasting for 27 October and beyond (i.e. the **seq** includes the mainshock and the sequence of the
523 events up to T_{start} of the corresponding date). This change is a rational (as well as an operational)
524 choice; e.g. for daily forecasting starting from 00.00 UTC on 27 October, 25 hours have passed since
525 the mainshock, and we have sufficient events (according to the second column of Table 5, **seq**
526 contains 101 events including the mainshock and the sequence of aftershocks with $M > M_c$). Thus,
527 there is no longer a need to use the catalogue before the mainshock. However, if we face a lack of
528 data in the catalogue after the mainshock, then, we would move the catalogue's start time back a
529 couple of days before the mainshock, in order to have sufficient data to perform the Bayesian
530 updating. This was not necessary for Sequence 'F', but, this assumption is necessary to make the
531 algorithm versatile. The magnitude of completeness, M_c , in Table 5 is equal to 4.1 (see the third
532 column). The retrospective forecasting results for the number of events with $M > 4.5$ are shown in
533 Table 5, which confirms that the forecasted number of events is in good agreement with the observed
534 data (see the last four columns in Table 5). However, an event with a magnitude (M_w) of 6.2 occurred
535 on 30 October at 02:59 UTC. The ETAS model cannot directly forecast such a severe doublet event.
536 Nevertheless, the forecasted number of earthquakes above the threshold of 4.5 is between 4 and 7,
537 which confirms that the seismicity is still high based on this forecasting model. As seen in Table 5,
538 the employed N-test results also confirm that, in all cases, the N_{obs} is not located within the tails of our
539 forecast.

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541

Table 5. The variation of the model parameters θ and seismicity forecasting results for seven days following the mainshock for sequence F (Table 1). The forecasting time interval is equal to 24 hours (1 day) for all seven days with $T_{start} = 00:00$ UTC at the corresponding date.

Forecast date (dd-mm)	No. of events after the mainshock ($M \geq M_c$)	M_c	β		c		p		d		q		Number of forecasted events with $M \geq 4.5$			Observed	N-test
			median	σ	median	σ	median	σ	median	σ	median	σ	Median	Median+1 σ	Median+2 σ		
26-10	8 (+68)	4.1	1.682	.002	.064	.007	1.008	.005	2.556	.151	1.226	.012	20	24	35	32	.983, .026
27-10	101	4.1	1.872	.102	.042	.007	1.558	.135	2.241	.266	1.338	.042	2	3	5	7	.988, .033
28-10	138	4.1	1.966	.112	.041	.008	1.273	.095	2.315	.224	1.330	.031	4	5	9	6	.889, .214
29-10	210	4.1	2.056	.091	.042	.007	1.180	.075	2.480	.228	1.354	.035	4	6	7	5	.785, .371
30-10	247	4.1	2.078	.099	.042	.007	1.109	.055	2.534	.196	1.373	.028	4	5	7	11	.989, .025
31-10	286	4.1	2.067	.068	.041	.007	1.079	.040	2.730	.221	1.383	.035	5	6	9	2	.238, .908
01-11	303	4.1	2.089	.079	.045	.008	1.110	.053	2.684	.194	1.381	.034	4	5	6	4	.628, .566

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543

544

545 In addition, the forecasting model is applied to the other sequences in Table 1 (A to E), starting about
 546 1 to 2 hours following their mainshocks. The forecasting results for the first 24 hours are shown in
 547 Figure 6 for sequences A to E. As seen in Figure 6, it is confirmed that the numbers of forecasted
 548 events are in good agreement with the observed data. Additionally, in all the six considered sequences
 549 the forecasted events' spatial distribution is also in good agreement with the observed data. This is
 550 evidence that the proposed model can reproduce seismic sequences surrounding a mainshock in the
 551 study area.

552 Figure 6. The spatial distribution of seismicity (the maps report the mean+2 σ confidence interval, i.e. 98th
 553 percentile, for the number of events per km²) in the aftershock zone for sequences A to E (Table 1) during one
 554 day following the mainshock. See the caption of Figure 5 for an explanation of the information.

555

556 As discussed earlier, one concern in the ETAS forecasting approach is how to select reasonable prior
 557 values for θ . The posterior distributions of θ , in the day following the mainshock, and for the six
 558 seismic sequences in Table 1, are shown in Table 6. The forecasting origin time, T_{start} , for each
 559 seismic sequence in Table 6 is identical to that shown in Figures 5 and 6. The median of the five
 560 model parameters of ETAS and their uncertainties are also provided in Table 6. Furthermore, the
 561 minimum and maximum values for each model parameter (in terms of the median and σ) are shown
 562 in the last row in Table 6, which we propose to be employed as a reasonable set of prior θ for further
 563 implementation in the study area. As seen in Table 6, parameters c and p do not change significantly,
 564 confirming that the temporal decay follows the MO's law in all the sequences. However, parameters β

565 and d vary significantly among the different sequences, which indicates that the spatial characteristics
 566 and the Gutenberg-Richter relation are sequence-specific. Additionally, it is worth emphasising that,
 567 as seen in Table 6, the ETAS posterior parameters are quite sequence-specific. Hence, using the
 568 proposed *incremental adaptive training algorithm* is a superior approach to using the model
 569 parameters from previous sequences in the study area.

570 Table 6. The posterior distributions of ETAS parameters for six sequences in Table 1. All the parameters are
 571 assumed normally distributed.

Sequence ID	β		c		p		d		q	
	median	σ	median	σ	median	σ	median	σ	median	σ
A	2.049	.001	.062	.008	1.010	.004	2.669	.221	1.195	.010
B	2.148	.016	.042	.008	1.018	.009	2.153	.216	1.187	.018
C	2.270	.012	.055	.007	1.010	.006	2.457	.212	1.217	.015
D	2.151	.091	.031	.008	1.033	.024	1.172	.199	1.182	.032
E	1.759	.069	.046	.007	1.012	.007	1.654	.193	1.216	.023
F	1.682	.002	.064	.007	1.008	.005	2.556	.151	1.226	.012
Bounds of parameters	1.682- 2.270	.001- .091	.031- .064	.007- .008	1.008- 1.033	.004- .024	1.172- 2.669	.151- .221	1.182- 1.226	.010- .032

572

573 6 SEISMIC HAZARD MODEL

574 The short-term changes in seismicity revealed by the ETAS model, reflected by the time-variant
 575 conditional rate in Equation 1, are superimposed on the background seismicity (see Equation 2) to
 576 forecast the number of events over the aftershock zone within the considered time interval. The
 577 seismicity output in terms of the forecasted number of events in the forecasting time interval can be
 578 used as the short-term seismicity rate within a short-term time-dependent PSHA. Therefore, firstly, a
 579 conventional PSHA has been performed using Equation 6 (adapted from Cornell 1968; McGuire
 580 1995; Ebrahimian et al 2014; Baker 2015; Ebrahimian et al. 2019; and numerically integrated over the
 581 aftershock zone):

$$582 \lambda(PGA > pga) = \lambda(M > M_{min}) \int_{M_{min}}^{M_{max}} \int_{X_{min}}^{X_{max}} \int_{Y_{min}}^{Y_{max}} P(PGA > \\ 583 pga | m, d\{(x, y), (x_s, y_s)\}) \cdot f_M(m) \cdot f_{X,Y}(x, y) dy dx dm \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

584 where $\lambda(PGA > pga)$ is the annual rate of exceedance of PGA above a threshold pga ; M_{min} is equal
 585 to 4.5 (the same assumption as in ESHM13); M_{max} is the maximum magnitude obtained from the
 586 ESHM13 results for each area source; $\lambda(M > M_{min})$ is the annual rate of exceedance of earthquakes
 587

588 greater than M_{min} , which is numerically defined for each grid cell based on the ESHM13 SEIFA
 589 model; $d\{(x, y), (x_s, y_s)\}$ is the epicentral distance between the desired site (x_s and y_s coordinates
 590 where the hazard computation is of interest) and an arbitrary point (x and y coordinates $\in \mathbf{A}$) inside
 591 the aftershock zone (see also Ebrahimian et al. 2019); $P(PGA > pga|m, d\{(x, y), (x_s, y_s)\})$ is the
 592 conditional probability of PGA exceeding a threshold pga , given a magnitude m and an epicentral
 593 distance d at the $(x, y \in \mathbf{A})$ coordinate which can be estimated using a Ground Motion Prediction
 594 Equation (GMPE); $f_M(m)$ is the probability density function of magnitude, which follows the
 595 Gutenberg-Richter relationship based on the ESHM13 for each area source; $f_{X,Y}(x, y)$ is the joint
 596 probability density function of the distance distribution at an arbitrary point with $(x, y \in \mathbf{A})$ from the
 597 site (x_s, y_s) coordinate, which has a uniform distribution, i.e. assuming equiprobable occurrence of
 598 earthquakes in the area source; X_{min} and X_{max} are, respectively, the lower and upper bound values in
 599 the x-axis direction in Cartesian coordinates inside the study area ($\in \mathbf{A}$); Y_{min} and Y_{max} are,
 600 respectively, the lower and upper bound values in the y-axis direction in Cartesian coordinates inside
 601 the study area ($\in \mathbf{A}$).

602 Choosing GMPEs for seismic hazard analysis has always been a challenging task (see also Danciu et
 603 al. 2007; Segou et al. 2010; Delavaud et al. 2012; Skarlatoudis et al. 2013). On the other hand, a
 604 sophisticated logic tree including several GMPEs makes the forecasting algorithm time consuming,
 605 thereby limiting its potential real-time use for OEF. Therefore, only three GMPEs are used in this
 606 study to approximately match the ESHM13 assumptions as well as recent GMPE developments for
 607 Greece: Chiou and Youngs (2014), with a weight of 25%, Zhao et al. (2006), with a weight of 25%,
 608 and Boore et al. (2021), with a weight of 50%. The 2008 version of Chiou and Youngs' GMPE has
 609 been used in ESHM13; however, we decided to use the newer version (Chiou and Youngs 2014). The
 610 Chiou and Youngs (2014) GMPE is also justified by this model's high stability (Bommer and Stafford
 611 2020). However, Zhao et al. (2006) GMPE was also chosen to account for epistemic uncertainty since
 612 it has the simplest functional form among the GMPEs used in the ESHM13. The Boore et al. (2021)
 613 GMPE was also taken into consideration since it has recently been developed specifically for Greece.
 614 Therefore, we allocate a higher, 50%, weight to this regional model. We also acknowledge that the

615 influence of GMPE selection on the final short-term time-dependent PSHA is an interesting topic for
 616 future research but it is beyond the scope of this study.

617 The short-term (daily) time-dependent PSHA is performed by substituting the rate $\lambda(M > M_{min})$ in
 618 Equation (6) by the forecasted number of events obtained from the robust seismicity framework
 619 (herein, corresponding to sequence F for 26 October 2018) and over the forecasting time interval (see
 620 Equation 4). The rest of the parameters have the same definition and values as used for the
 621 background (time-independent) hazard calculations. The aftershock zone is subdivided into 14 area
 622 sources as defined in ESHM13 and shown in Figure 7. The results of the conventional and time-
 623 dependent PSHA are shown in Figure 8 for Patras city. The left graph in Figure 8 is for the daily
 624 probability of exceedance, and the right graph is for the daily rate of exceedance. It is assumed that a
 625 Poisson process models the occurrence of earthquakes of interest. It is worth mentioning that a
 626 complex logic-tree is not recommended for OEF, since the computational effort should be kept to a
 627 minimum level to obtain the forecasts as rapidly as possible.

628
 629 Figure 7. 14 area sources in the study area from ESHM13 (Giardini et al. 2013; Woessner et al. 2015).

630
 631 In the next step, $\lambda(M > M_{min})$ is altered with the expected number of events within the forecasting
 632 interval (herein, 1-day) resulting from the implemented seismicity forecasting framework to account
 633 for the summation of background seismicity (from conventional PSHA) and short-term seismicity
 634 (see Equation 4). The hazard integral (Equation 5) is computed again based on this increased short-
 635 term seismicity. The results of this time-dependent PSHA are shown in the left (daily probability of
 636 exceedance) and the right (daily rate of exceedance) panels in Figure 8 for Patras on 26 October 2018.
 637 For the purpose of comparison with the conventional PSHA, the annual frequency of exceedance
 638 derived from the long-term (time-independent) hazard is converted to the daily rate (dividing by 365)
 639 and consequently transformed into the daily probability of exceedance using the Poisson distribution.
 640 It is worth mentioning that the conventional hazard curve represents a lower bound for this short-term
 641 hazard curve, since we assume that the short-term seismicity can only increase the long-term hazard.

642

643

644 Figure 8. Short-term PSHA for Patras, (left): the short-term time-dependent daily probability of exceedance
 645 versus PGA and comparison with the conventional daily hazard curve, and (right): short-term time-dependent
 646 daily rate of exceedance versus PGA and comparison with the conventional daily hazard curve.

647

648 The short-term hazard ratio to the median conventional hazard is defined as the *Probability Gain*
 649 (PG), which is a function of the considered PGA . As can be seen in Figure 8, the PG parameter
 650 decreases as PGA increases. The PG parameter, corresponding to a PGA equal to $0.05g$, is calculated
 651 for all the cells inside the study area and the results are shown in Figure 9 in terms of 2nd, 50th, and

652 98th percentiles. These percentiles are based on the dispersion of the forecasted number of events
653 obtained from the robust seismicity framework. It is worth mentioning that the background seismicity
654 is kept to the median value for all three cases. The maximum PG values occur around the mainshock's
655 epicentre, and equal 321, 385, and 448, respectively, in the cases of 2nd (Figure 9-top), 50th (Figure 9-
656 middle), and 98th percentiles (Figure 9-bottom). However, the colour bar in Figure 9 is limited to 100
657 to better distinguish the differences amongst the cells.

658 Figure 9. The spatial distribution of the PG parameter (the ratio of short-term hazard to the long-term time-
 659 independent hazard corresponding to a *PGA* equal to 0.05g) for sequence F (Table 1). The forecast starts at
 660 00:00UTC on 26 October 2018 and for the next 24 hours. (top): 2nd percentile, (middle): 50th percentile, and
 661 (bottom): 98th percentile.
 662

663 PG can also be considered for a given site with respect to time since the mainshock. The variation of
 664 the 50th percentile PG for the cities of Patras and Aegio is shown in Figure 10 for all the sequences in
 665 Table 1 during the four days following each sequence’s mainshock. The results reveal that the
 666 heightened seismicity decays rapidly during the first two days (the so-called “golden hours” for first
 667 responders) following the mainshock. The 50th percentile PG is as high as 33 in Aegio (23 km from
 668 the epicentre of the mainshock of sequence A, see Table 1) during the first hours following the
 669 mainshock whereas, the 50th percentile PG equals 17 in Patras (50 km from the epicentre) in this time
 670 period. As seen in Figure 10, the same trend is seen for sequence C (see Table 1), the second closest
 671 event to the studied cities among the six selected sequences. The other seismic sequences show lower

672 PG values (mostly less than 10) since their mainshock epicentres are far from the studied cities. For
 673 example, the 50th percentile PG value is about 3 in the case of sequence F (starting on 26 October
 674 2018), which can also be seen in Figure 8 for a *PGA* equal to 0.05g.

675 Figure 10. The median probability gain PG (the ratio of the median short-term time-dependent to the median
 676 long-term time-independent hazard corresponding to a *PGA* equal to 0.05g) versus days since the mainshock at
 677 Patras and Aegio for the different seismic sequences in Table 1.
 678

679 7 CONCLUSIONS

680 A robust seismicity forecasting framework has been applied using the ISC earthquake catalogue for
 681 western Greece, one of the most seismically active regions in Europe. The chosen catalogue was used
 682 to identify six aftershock sequences between 1995 to 2018 with at least one mainshock with moment
 683 magnitude $M_w \geq 6$. A new approach has been introduced for incrementally adaptive training of the
 684 ETAS model parameters prior to the mainshock, which can be further used to start forecasting quickly
 685 after the mainshock. The developed algorithm facilitates the concept of operational earthquake
 686 forecasting, which aims at forecasting damaging earthquakes during the first golden hours after a
 687 severe mainshock. It is worth emphasising that the employed algorithm takes advantage of Bayesian

688 inference, in contrast to the majority of the available studies which use constant ETAS coefficients.
689 The forecasting algorithm is applied for the next 24 hours to forecast the spatial distribution of the
690 seismicity rate and the number of potentially damaging earthquakes (here defined as an event with a
691 moment magnitude $M_w \geq 4.5$). In addition, the proposed algorithm has been tested to demonstrate its
692 usability for operational forecasting on the basis of intervals of 6 hours to 7 days. The results show
693 that the adapted ETAS model within the seismicity framework can retrospectively forecast the
694 number of damaging earthquakes and that the forecasts are generally in good agreement with the
695 observed data. The spatial distribution of the heightened seismicity zone is also in good agreement
696 with the spatial propagation of observed events. This seismicity forecasting framework has been
697 applied to the six selected seismic sequences, and posterior distributions of the model parameters
698 were obtained by employing Bayesian inference. These distributions and their relative bounds are
699 proposed as prior values for future forecasting of new aftershock sequences in the region. The results
700 of the current study reveal that the temporal decay of events follows almost the same MO's law for all
701 sequences; however, the spatial and magnitude-frequency (Gutenberg-Richter) characteristics are
702 sequence-specific.

703 The forecasted occurrence rates were implemented within a time-dependent seismic hazard
704 framework using inputs on the long-term seismicity from ESHM13. The daily seismic hazard was
705 computed for the study area as well as for the two major cities of the study region, Patras and Aegio.
706 The results revealed that the daily probability of exceeding a threshold PGA equal to $0.05g$ is, on
707 average, increased by up to 33 times the long-term (time-independent) hazard in Aegio, during the
708 first hours following the 1995 M_w 6.5 mainshock. This PG parameter decays to under 10 after three
709 days. Additionally, the PG parameter varies between 1 and 10 for the four seismic sequences (B, D, E
710 and F) that are relatively far from the considered cities. It is important to note that multiple types of
711 uncertainty have been addressed in the proposed forecasting framework, such as Bayesian inference
712 and MCMC simulations in the ETAS forecasting model, and GMPE and logic-tree in the hazard
713 model. However, the optimum choice of GMPE and associated logic-tree weights for this region, and
714 more generally for operational earthquake forecasting globally, remains an interesting topic for future

715 research. Also, considering uncertainties from different sources such as the PSHA and forecasting
716 algorithms is an area to be explored in future.

717 The current study has demonstrated the applicability of the proposed forecasting algorithm for short-
718 time intervals (by emphasising medium-to-large events), which is of great interest for first responders
719 during an aftershock sequence. The forecasted distribution was in good agreement with the observed
720 events in all retrospectively-studied earthquake sequences. Besides, the spatial distribution of
721 forecasted events was close to the distribution of observed events. Therefore, at least within the
722 assumption and limitations of the present study, it is concluded that the employed Bayesian inference
723 has the ability to be adapted to the specific characteristics of earthquakes in this region.

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732 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

733 Earthquake catalogue data were provided by ISC (last accessed 2020). The data regarding this article
734 can be found online at <https://earthquake-turnkey.eu/> or by contacting the corresponding author.

735 **REFERENCES**

736 Azarbakht, A., Rudman, A., & Douglas, J. (2021). A decision-making approach for operational
737 earthquake forecasting. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, **66**, p1-13.

- 738 Baker, J. W. (2015) Introduction to Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis. White Paper Version 2.1,
739 77 pp.
- 740 Beck, J. L. & Au, S. K. (2002) Bayesian updating of structural models and reliability using Markov
741 Chain Monte Carlo simulation. *Journal of Engineering Mechanics ASCE*, **128**(4), 380-391.
- 742 Bommer, J. J., & Stafford, P. J. (2020). Selecting Ground-Motion Models for Site-Specific PSHA:
743 Adaptability versus Applicability. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **110**(6), 2801-
744 2815.
- 745 Bondár, I., & Storchak, D. (2011). Improved location procedures at the International Seismological
746 Centre. *Geophysical Journal International*, **186**(3), 1220-1244.
- 747 Boore, D. M., Stewart, J. P., Skarlatoudis, A. A., Seyhan, E., Margaris, B., Theodoulidis, N.,
748 Scordilis, E., Kalogeras, I., Klimis, N. and Melis, N. S. (2021). A ground-motion prediction model for
749 shallow crustal earthquakes in Greece. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **111**(2), 857-
750 874. Cattania, C., Werner, M. J., Marzocchi, W., Hainzl, S., Rhoades, D., Gerstenberger, M., ... &
751 Jordan, T. H. (2018). The forecasting skill of physics-based seismicity models during the 2010-2012
752 Canterbury, New Zealand, earthquake sequence. *Seismological Research Letters*, 89(4), 1238-1250.
- 753 Chiou, B. S. J., & Youngs, R. R. (2014). Update of the Chiou and Youngs NGA model for the
754 average horizontal component of peak ground motion and response spectra. *Earthquake*
755 *Spectra*, **30**(3), 1117-1153.
- 756 Console, R., Rhoades, D. A., Murru, M., Evison, F. F., Papadimitriou, E. E., & Karakostas, V. G.
757 (2006). Comparative performance of time-invariant, long-range and short-range forecasting models
758 on the earthquake catalogue of Greece. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, **111**(B9).
- 759 Console, R., Murru, M., Catalli, F., Falcone, G. (2007). Real time forecasts through an earthquake
760 clustering model constrained by the rate-and-state constitutive law: comparison with a purely
761 stochastic ETAS model. *Seismological Research Letters*, **78**(1), 49–56.

- 762 Cornell, C. A. (1968). Engineering seismic risk analysis. *Bulletin of the seismological society of*
763 *America*, **58**(5), 1583-1606.
- 764 Daley, D. J., & Vere-Jones, D. (2008). An introduction to the theory of point processes: volume II:
765 general theory and structure. *Springer New York*.
- 766 Danciu, L., & Tselentis, G. A. (2007). Engineering ground-motion parameters attenuation
767 relationships for Greece. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **97**(1B), 162-183.
- 768 Delavaud, E., Cotton, F., Akkar, S., Scherbaum, F., Danciu, L., Beauval, C., Drouet, S., Douglas, J.,
769 Basili, R., Sandikkaya, M.A. and Segou, M. (2012). Toward a ground-motion logic tree for
770 probabilistic seismic hazard assessment in Europe. *Journal of Seismology*, **16**(3), 451-473.
- 771 Douglas, J., & Azarbakht, A. (2021). Cost–benefit analyses to assess the potential of Operational
772 Earthquake Forecasting prior to a mainshock in Europe. *Natural Hazards*, **105**(1), 293-311.
- 773 Drakatos, G., & Latoussakis, J. (1996). Some features of aftershock patterns in Greece. *Geophysical*
774 *Journal International*, **126**(1), 123-134.
- 775 Ebrahimian H., Jalayer F. (2021). Operational Aftershock Forecasting for 2017-2018 Seismic
776 Sequence in Western Iran. *EGU General Assembly*, Online, 19-30 April 2021, EGU21-15824,
777 <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-15824>.
- 778 Ebrahimian, H., Jalayer, F., Forte, G., Convertito, V., Licata, V., d’Onofrio, A., ... & Manfredi, G.
779 (2019). Site-specific probabilistic seismic hazard analysis for the western area of Naples,
780 Italy. *Bulletin of earthquake engineering*, **17**(9), 4743-4796.
- 781 Ebrahimian, H., & Jalayer, F. (2017). Robust seismicity forecasting based on Bayesian parameter
782 estimation for epidemiological spatio-temporal aftershock clustering models. *Scientific reports*, **7**(1),
783 1-15.

- 784 Ebrahimian, H., Jalayer, F., Asprone, D., Lombardi, A. M., Marzocchi, W., Prota, A., & Manfredi, G.
785 (2014). Adaptive daily forecasting of seismic aftershock hazard. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society*
786 *of America*, **104**(1), 145-161.
- 787 Ebrahimian H., Jalayer F., Asprone D., Lombardi A.M., Marzocchi W., Prota A., Manfredi G. (2014).
788 A performance-based framework for adaptive seismic aftershock vulnerability assessment.
789 *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*, 43(14): 2179-2197.
- 790 Ebrahimian H., Jalayer F., Asprone D., Lombardi A.M., Marzocchi W., Prota A., and Manfredi G.
791 (2013). An outlook into time-dependent aftershock vulnerability assessment. *4th ECCOMAS Thematic*
792 *Conference on Computational Methods in Structural Dynamics and Earthquake Engineering*
793 *(COMPADYN2013)*, M. Papadrakakis, V. Papadopoulos, V. Plevris (eds.), Kos Island, Greece, 12-14
794 June 2013.
- 795 Field, E. H., & Milner, K. R. (2018). Candidate products for operational earthquake forecasting
796 illustrated using the HayWired planning scenario, including one very quick (and not-so-dirty)
797 hazard-map option. *Seismological Research Letters*, 89(4), 1420-1434.
- 798 Giardini, D, J Woessner, L Danciu, H Crowley, F Cotton, G Grünthal, R Pinho, et al., 2013. Seismic
799 Hazard Harmonisation in Europe (SHARE): Online Data Resource. doi: 10.12686/SED-00000001-
800 *SHARE*.
- 801 Goltz, J. D., 2015. A Further Note on Operational Earthquake Forecasting: An Emergency
802 Management Perspective. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **86**(5) 1231-1233.
- 803 Gospodinov, D., Karakostas, V., Papadimitriou, E., & Ranguelov, B. (2007). Analysis of relaxation
804 temporal patterns in Greece through the RETAS model approach. *Physics of the Earth and Planetary*
805 *Interiors*, **165**(3-4), 158-175.

- 806 Gospodinov, D., & Rotondi, R. RETAS: a restricted ETAS model inspired by Bath's law. The 4th
807 International Workshop on Statistical Seismology – The Graduate University for Advanced Studies,
808 Shonan Village campus, Kanagawa Prefecture, Japan, 9-13 January, 2006.
- 809 Hainzl, S., Christophersen, A., & Enescu, B. (2008). Impact of earthquake rupture extensions on
810 parameter estimations of point-process models. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*,
811 98(4), 2066-2072.
- 812 Hainzl, S., Zakharova, O., & Marsan, D. (2013). Impact of aseismic transients on the estimation of
813 aftershock productivity parameters. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 103(3), 1723-
814 1732.
- 815 Harte, D. S. (2013). Bias in fitting the ETAS model: a case study based on New Zealand seismicity.
816 *Geophysical Journal International*, 192(1), 390-412.
- 817 Hastings, W. K. (1970). Monte-Carlo sampling methods using Markov chains and their applications.
818 *Biometrika*, 57(1), 97-109.
- 819 International Seismological Centre (2020), On-line Bulletin, <https://doi.org/10.31905/D808B830>
- 820 Jordan, T. H., Marzocchi, W., Michael, A. J., & Gerstenberger, M. C. 2014. Operational Earthquake
821 Forecasting Can Enhance Earthquake Preparedness. *Seismological Research Letters*, **85**(5): 955–59.
- 822 Jordan, T. H., & Jones, L. M. (2010). Operational earthquake forecasting: Some thoughts on why and
823 how. *Seismological Research Letters*, **81**(4), 571-574.
- 824 Karagianni, E., Paradisopoulou, P., & Karakostas, V. (2013). Spatio-temporal earthquake clustering in
825 the Western Corinth Gulf. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Greece*, **47**(3), 1109-1117.
- 826 Karakostas, V., Kostoglou, A., Chorozioglou, D., & Papadimitriou, E. (2020). Relocation of the 2018
827 Zakynthos, Greece, aftershock sequence: spatiotemporal analysis deciphering mechanism diversity
828 and aftershock statistics. *Acta Geophysica*, **68**(5), 1263-1294.

- 829 Karakostas, V., Papadimitriou, E., & Gospodinov, D. (2014). Modelling the 2013 North Aegean
830 (Greece) seismic sequence: geometrical and frictional constraints, and aftershock
831 probabilities. *Geophysical Journal International*, **197**(1), 525-541.
- 832 Kourouklas, C., Mangira, O., Iliopoulos, A., Chorozioglou, D., & Papadimitriou, E. (2020). A study of
833 short-term spatiotemporal clustering features of Greek seismicity. *Journal of Seismology*, **24**, 459-
834 477.
- 835 Latoussakis, J., & Drakatos, G. (1994). A quantitative study of some aftershock sequences in
836 Greece. *pure and applied geophysics*, **143**(4), 603-616.
- 837 Latoussakis, J., Stavrakakis, G., Drakopoulos, J., Papanastassiou, D., & Drakatos, G. (1991).
838 Temporal characteristics of some earthquake sequences in Greece. *Tectonophysics*, **193**(4), 299-310.
- 839 Lippiello, E., Petrillo, G., Godano, C., Tramelli, A., Papadimitriou, E., & Karakostas, V. (2019).
840 Forecasting of the first hour aftershocks by means of the perceived magnitude. *Nature*
841 *communications*, **10**(1), 1-10.
- 842 Lippiello, E., Cirillo, A., Godano, G., Papadimitriou, E., & Karakostas, V. (2016). Real-time forecast
843 of aftershocks from a single seismic station signal. *Geophysical Research Letters*, **43**(12), 6252-6258.
- 844 Lippiello, E., Giacco, F., Arcangelis, L. D., Marzocchi, W., & Godano, C. (2014). Parameter
845 estimation in the ETAS model: Approximations and novel methods. *Bulletin of the Seismological*
846 *Society of America*, **104**(2), 985-994.
- 847 Lippiello, E., Marzocchi, W., De Arcangelis, L., & Godano, C. (2012). Spatial organisation of
848 foreshocks as a tool to forecast large earthquakes. *Scientific reports*, **2**(1), 1-6.
- 849 Marzocchi, W., & Lombardi, A. M. (2009). Real-time forecasting following a damaging earthquake.
850 *Geophysical Research Letters*, **36**(21).

- 851 Marzocchi, W., and M. Murru (2012), Daily earthquake forecasts during the May–June 2012 Emilia
852 earthquake sequence (northern Italy), *Annals of Geophysics*, 55(4), 561–567, doi:10.4401/ag-6161.
- 853 Marzocchi, W., Lombardi, A. M., & Casarotti, E. (2014). The establishment of an operational
854 earthquake forecasting system in Italy. *Seismological Research Letters* 85(5): 961-969.
- 855 Mangira, O., Console, R., Papadimitriou, E., Murru, M., & Karakostas, V. (2020). The short-term
856 seismicity of the Central Ionian Islands (Greece) studied by means of a clustering model. *Geophysical*
857 *Journal International*, 220(2), 856-875.
- 858 McBride, S. K., Llenos, A. L., Page, M. T., & Van Der Elst, N. (2020). # EarthquakeAdvisory:
859 Exploring discourse between government officials, news media, and social media during the 2016
860 Bombay Beach Swarm. *Seismological Research Letters*, 91(1), 438-451.
- 861 McGuire, R. K. (1995). Probabilistic seismic hazard analysis and design earthquakes: closing the
862 loop. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, 85(5), 1275-1284.
- 863 Metropolis, N., Rosenbluth, A. W., Rosenbluth, M. N., Teller, A. H., Teller, E. (1953). Equations of
864 state calculations by fast computing machines. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 21(6), 1087-1092.
- 865 Ogata, Y., & Zhuang, J. (2006). Space–time ETAS models and an improved
866 extension. *Tectonophysics*, 413(1-2), 13-23.
- 867 Ogata, Y. (1998). Space-time point-process models for earthquake occurrences. *Annals of the Institute*
868 *of Statistical Mathematics*, 50(2), 379-402.
- 869 Ogata, Y. (1988). Statistical models for earthquake occurrences and residual analysis for point
870 processes. *Journal of the American Statistical association*, 83(401), 9-27.
- 871 Omi, T., Ogata, Y., Hirata, Y., & Aihara, K. (2015). Intermediate-term forecasting of aftershocks
872 from an early aftershock sequence: Bayesian and ensemble forecasting approaches. *Journal of*
873 *Geophysical Research: Solid Earth*, 120(4), 2561-2578.

- 874 Papadimitriou, C., Beck, J. L., & Katafygiotis, L. S. (2001). Updating robust reliability using
875 structural test data. *Probabilistic engineering mechanics*, **16**(2), 103-113.
- 876 Papadopoulos, A. N., Bazzurro, P., & Marzocchi, W. (2021). Exploring probabilistic seismic risk
877 assessment accounting for seismicity clustering and damage accumulation: Part I. Hazard analysis.
878 *Earthquake Spectra*, **37**(2), 803-826.
- 879 Papaioannou, C. A., & Papazachos, B. C. (2000). Time-independent and time-dependent seismic
880 hazard in Greece based on seismogenic sources. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of*
881 *America*, **90**(1), 22-33.
- 882 Roeloffs, E., & Goltz, J. (2017). The California earthquake advisory plan: A history. *Seismological*
883 *Research Letters*, **88**(3), 784-797.
- 884 Segou, M. (2016). Physics-based and statistical earthquake forecasting in a continental rift zone: the
885 case study of Corinth Gulf (Greece). *Geophysical Journal International*, **204**(1), 591-605.
- 886 Segou, M., Voulgaris, N., & Makropoulos, K. (2010). On the sensitivity of ground motion prediction
887 equations in Greece. *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Greece*, **43**(4), 2163-2173.
- 888 Skarlatoudis, A. A., Papazachos, C. B., Margaris, B. N., Ventouzi, C., Kalogeras, I., & EGELADOS
889 Group. (2013). Ground-motion prediction equations of intermediate-depth earthquakes in the Hellenic
890 arc, southern Aegean subduction area. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **103**(3), 1952-
891 1968.
- 892 Telesca, L., Cuomo, V., Lapenna, V., Vallianatos, F., & Drakatos, G. (2001). Analysis of the temporal
893 properties of Greek aftershock sequences. *Tectonophysics*, **341**(1-4), 163-178.
- 894 Tsapanos, T. M. (2008). Seismicity and seismic hazard assessment in Greece. In *Earthquake*
895 *monitoring and seismic hazard mitigation in Balkan countries* (pp. 253-270). Springer, Dordrecht.

- 896 Utsu, T. and Ogata, Y. 1995. The Centenary of the Omori Formula for a Decay Law of Aftershock
897 Activity. *Journal of Physics of the Earth*, **43**(1): 1–33.
- 898 Utsu, T. (1961). A statistical study on the occurrence of aftershocks. *Geophys. Mag.*, **30**, 521-605.
- 899 Vamvakaris, D. A., Papazachos, C. B., Papaioannou, C. A., Scordilis, E. M., & Karakaisis, G. F.
900 (2016). A detailed seismic zonation model for shallow earthquakes in the broader Aegean
901 area. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, **16**(1), 55-84.
- 902 Wiemer, S. (2001). A software package to analyse seismicity: ZMAP. *Seismological Research*
903 *Letters*, **72**(3), 373-382.
- 904 Woessner, J., Laurentiu, D., Giardini, D., Crowley, H., Cotton, F., Grünthal, G., ... & Stucchi, M.
905 (2015). The 2013 European seismic hazard model: key components and results. *Bulletin of*
906 *Earthquake Engineering*, **13**(12), 3553-3596.
- 907 Zechar, J. D., Gerstenberger, M. C., Rhoades, D. A. (2010). Likelihood-based tests for evaluating
908 space–rate–magnitude earthquake forecasts. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*
909 **100**(3):1184-1195.
- 910 Zhang, X., & Shcherbakov, R. (2016). Power-law rheology controls aftershock triggering and
911 decay. *Scientific reports*, **6**(1), 1-9.
- 912 Zhao, J. X., Zhang, J., Asano, A., Ohno, Y., Oouchi, T., Takahashi, T., ... & Fukushima, Y. (2006).
913 Attenuation relations of strong ground motion in Japan using site classification based on predominant
914 period. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, **96**(3), 898-913.
- 915 Zhuang, J. (2011). Next-day earthquake forecasts for the Japan region generated by the ETAS model.
916 *Earth, planets and space*, **63**(3), 207-216.

917 Zhuang, J., Werner, M. J., Hainzl, S., Harte, D., Zhou, S. (2011). *Basic models of seismicity:*
 918 *spatiotemporal models*. Community Online Resource for Statistical Seismicity Analysis,
 919 doi:10.5078/corssa-07487583.

920 **APPENDIX 1**

921 **Sampling θ from the distribution $p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l)$**

922 The probability distribution $p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l)$ in Equation (3) can be calculated using Bayesian parameter
 923 estimation as follows (see also Ebrahimian and Jalayer 2017):

$$924 \quad p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l) = C^{-1} p(\text{seq}|\theta, M_l) \cdot p(\theta|M_l) \quad (\text{Eq. A1})$$

925 where $p(\text{seq}|\theta, M_l)$ denotes the likelihood of the observed sequence given the vector of model
 926 parameters θ and lower cut-off magnitude M_l , $p(\theta|M_l)$ is the prior distribution for the vector θ , and
 927 the term C^{-1} is a normalizing constant. In lieu of additional information (e.g., statistics of regional
 928 model parameters), the prior joint distribution $p(\theta|M_l)$ can be estimated as the product of marginal
 929 uniform probability distributions for each model parameter. The calculation of the likelihood
 930 $p(\text{seq}|\theta, M_l)$ is discussed in detail in Ebrahimian and Jalayer (2017).

931 In order to sample from $p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l)$, a MCMC simulation routine is employed, which is particularly
 932 useful for cases where the sampling needs to be done from a probability distribution that is known up
 933 to a constant value, that is C^{-1} herein (see Beck and Au 2002). The MCMC routine uses the
 934 Metropolis-Hastings (MH) algorithm (Metropolis et al. 1953, Hasting 1970) in order to generate
 935 samples as a Markov Chain sequence used first to sample from the target probability distribution
 936 $p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l)$, and later to estimate the robust seismicity forecasting in Equation (3) and Equation (4).
 937 The MH routine generates a Markov chain that produces a sequence of samples
 938 $[\theta_1 \rightarrow \theta_2 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \theta_n \rightarrow \dots]$, where θ_n represents the state of Markov Chain at n th iteration. It can be
 939 shown that the samples from the chain after the initial transient ones (the first few samples are often
 940 discarded to reduce the initial transient effect) reflect samples from the target distribution
 941 $p(\theta|\text{seq}, M_l)$. To generate the $(n+1)$ th sample θ_{n+1} given that the n th sample θ_n is already known, the
 942 following procedure is performed:

- 943 (a) Generate a candidate sample θ^* from a proposal (candidate) distribution $q(\theta|\theta_n)$. It is important to
 944 note that there are no specific restrictions about the choice of $q(\cdot)$ apart from the fact that it
 945 should be possible to calculate both $q(\theta_{i+1}|\theta_i)$ and $q(\theta_i|\theta_{i+1})$.
 946 (b) Accept the candidate sample with the probability $\min(1,r)$ (where r is defined in Equation (A2)
 947 as follows) and set $\theta_{n+1}=\theta^*$; otherwise, $\theta_{n+1}=\theta_n$:

$$948 \quad r = \frac{p(\theta^*|\text{seq},M_I) \cdot q(\theta_n|\theta^*)}{p(\theta_n|\text{seq},M_I) \cdot q(\theta^*|\theta_n)} = \left(\frac{p(\text{seq}|\theta^*,M_I)}{p(\text{seq}|\theta_n,M_I)} \cdot \frac{p(\theta^*|M_I)}{p(\theta_n|M_I)} \right) \cdot \frac{q(\theta_n|\theta^*)}{q(\theta^*|\theta_n)} \quad (\text{Eq. A2})$$

949 where $\frac{p(\text{seq}|\theta^*,M_I)}{p(\text{seq}|\theta_n,M_I)}$ is the likelihood ratio; $\frac{p(\theta^*|M_I)}{p(\theta_n|M_I)}$ is the prior ratio; $\frac{q(\theta_n|\theta^*)}{q(\theta^*|\theta_n)}$ is the proposal ratio.

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 951 It can be shown, see Beck and Au (2002); Jalayer and Ebrahimian (2017), using the Total Probability
 952 Theorem that, if the current sample θ_n is distributed as $p(\cdot|\text{seq},M_I)$, the $(n+1)^{\text{th}}$ sample θ_{n+1} is also
 953 distributed as $p(\cdot|\text{seq},M_I)$. In order to improve the rate of convergence of the simulation process, we
 954 have used an adaptive MH algorithm, as proposed by Beck and Au (2002), that introduces a sequence
 955 of intermediate evolutionary candidate PDF's that resemble more and more the target PDF.

956 APPENDIX 2- LIST OF SYMBOLS

Symbol	Meaning	Symbol	Meaning
Mw	Moment magnitude	$N_b(x, y, m M_I)$	a constant representing the area's background seismicity
A	Aftershock zone	$\mathbb{E}[N(x, y, m \text{seq}, M_I)]$	the average number of events in the cell centred at (x, y) with a magnitude $\geq m$ in the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$
λ_{ETAS}	The conditional rate of occurrence of earthquakes	Ω_{θ}	the domain of the model parameters
θ	Model parameters	$p(\theta \text{seq}, M_I)$	conditional posterior

				probability density function (PDF) for θ given the \mathbf{seq} and the lower cut-off magnitude M_l
\mathbf{seq}_t	past events		\mathbf{seqg}	the events within the forecasting interval
M_l	lower cut-off magnitude		$p(\mathbf{seqg} \theta, \mathbf{seq}, M_l)$	the PDF for the generated sequence \mathbf{seqg} given that θ and \mathbf{seq} are known
M_c	Magnitude completeness	of 'M'		Number of months before the forecast interval when applying the <i>incremental adaptive training algorithm</i>
β	related to the Gutenberg-Richter relation	the 'E'		arbitrary subsets of events with magnitude $\geq M_c$ when applying the <i>incremental adaptive training algorithm</i>
c and p	MO's Law parameter	'D'		Each 'E' subset covers at least 'D' days of the catalogue when applying the <i>incremental adaptive training algorithm</i>
d and q	spatial distribution of the triggered events	σ		Standard deviation
K	calibration for each forecasting interval		$\lambda(PGA > pga)$	the annual rate of exceedance of PGA

			above a threshold pga
K_t	Unifies the time-dependent term over infinite time	M_{min}	The minimum magnitude in PSHA
K_R	Unifies the spatial term over infinite space	M_{max}	The maximum magnitude in PSHA
α	efficiency of an event in generating aftershock activity	$\lambda(M > M_{min})$	the annual rate of exceedance of earthquakes greater than M_{min}
$[T_{start}, T_{end}]$	forecasting interval	$P(PGA > pga m, d\{(x, y), (x_s, y_s)\})$	the conditional probability of PGA exceeding a threshold pga , given a magnitude m and a epicentral distance d at the $(x, y \in \mathbf{A})$
T_o	time of origin	$f_M(m)$	probability density function of magnitude
seq	The observation history of N_o events that took place before the forecasting interval $[T_o, T_{start})$	$f_{x,y}(x, y)$	the joint probability density function of the distance distribution
$N(x, y, m \mathbf{seq}, M_t)$	The number of events at the centre point of a given cell centred at (x, y) with magnitude $\geq m$ in the forecasting interval $[T_{start}, T_{end}]$		